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RESEARCH ON DESIGN TECHNOLOGY OF SIMULATING PLATES FOR COMPRESSOR TOTAL PRESSURE DISTORTION

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ABSTRACT

Aerodynamic stability testing of compressors requires the use of distortion generators to simulate the inlet total pressure distortion flow field. Traditional design of such generators involves a repetitive process of trial-and-error, testing, and modification, which leads to long design cycles and difficulties in ensuring accuracy. This paper, based on the principle of boundary vorticity, investigates the design technology for simulating plate-type total pressure distortion generators. The influence of geometric features such as the width, height, and edge shape of the simulating plate on the downstream flow field structure and distortion parameters is analyzed. An intrinsic relationship between the simulating plate contour and the vorticity distribution is discovered, and the mechanism by which vortex pairs cause the expansion of the low-pressure region is revealed. Based on this mechanism, a design method is developed to inversely design the shape of the simulating plate according to the vorticity distribution to control the low-pressure region's configuration. The area of the low-pressure region is then precisely controlled by adjusting the geometrically similar contours of the plate. This method achieves the desired profile of the simulating plate in just two iterations, providing an effective technique for high-efficiency and high-precision distortion simulation in compressor aerodynamic stability tests.

Keywords: Distortion generator, Simulating plates, Total pressure distortion, Vorticity control, Numerical simulation

AIP Aerodynamic Interface Plane
DC(120) Circumferential total pressure distortion index
DES Detached Eddy Simulation

1. INTRODUCTION

With the continuous improvement of aircraft flight speed, altitude, and maneuverability, the compressor's inlet flow field deteriorates sharply, severely impacting the engine's stable operation [1-4]. Furthermore, as the stage loading of compressors continues to increase, their sensitivity to inlet distortion becomes progressively higher, making the issue of aerodynamic stability increasingly prominent. Consequently, it is necessary to conduct compressor stability tests for various operating conditions during the design phase, which requires the simulation of corresponding distortion patterns at the engine inlet. According to the operating conditions and flight envelope of aero-engine gas turbine compression systems, total pressure distortion is the most significant external factor that degrades aerodynamic stability [5-7].

FIGURE 1: TYPICAL DISTORTION GENERATORS

Current distortion generators include simulating screens, flat baffles, and simulating plates.

Simulating screens represent the earliest technology for total pressure distortion simulation; they use wire meshes of varying diameters and porosities assembled into a screen to generate total pressure distortion via the downstream aerodynamic wake. This method of distortion generation has been widely adopted in countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and Germany. Overall [8] developed a program that combines screen sections of different porosities,

NOMENCLATURE

D	Inner diameter of the inlet duct
H	Relative height of the simulating plate
h	Absolute height of the simulating plate
L	Relative width of the simulating plate
P_0	Average static pressure at the inlet plane
P_{t0}	Mass-flow averaged total pressure at the inlet plane
$P_{t_{low}}$	Mass-flow averaged total pressure in the most distorted 120-degree sector at the AIP
Q	Q-criterion for vortex identification
Y^+	Dimensionless wall distance
θ	Central angle

using isentropic flow area calculations to construct the total pressure distortion profile. However, after constructing the initial screen, it must be tested under actual operating conditions. The resulting distortion pattern is then compared with the desired total pressure field, followed by a repetitive process of screen design, fabrication, and testing until the required profile is achieved within an acceptable margin of error, typically requiring 4-6 physical screen iterations. Savage et al. [9] used a distortion generator composed of an array of individually controlled wedges, with an analytical model providing a rapid and reliable configuration scheme to generate specific distortion patterns. Ferrar et al. [10] utilized a flow-control grid composed of hexagonal elements with airfoil cross-sections, which improved aerodynamic and flow-control characteristics, thereby achieving greater design flexibility and accuracy.

However, the application of simulating screen distortion generators is limited to the simulation of steady-state total pressure distortion patterns, making it difficult to replicate dynamic total pressure distortion.

Regarding research on flat baffle-type distortion generators, Russia has accumulated considerable experience, conducting numerous experiments with scaled-down models and establishing relevant databases. Aiguo et al. [11] experimentally studied a dual-baffle distortion generator to expand the range of distortion simulation; Tu et al. [12] controlled the blockage coefficient and the total pressure distortion coefficient in their experiments by adjusting the insertion depth of the flat baffles and the mass flow rate. The results indicated a positive correlation between the total pressure distortion coefficient and the blockage coefficient. Zhou et al. [13] conducted high-resolution experimental measurements using flat baffles and performed comparative unsteady numerical simulations with Detached Eddy Simulation (DES), providing a basis for mutual validation between the numerical and experimental results. Chen et al. [14] investigated the total pressure distortion characteristics generated by inserting a single flat plate into an inlet duct, providing a direct experimental basis for the aerodynamic stability design and inlet distortion suppression for aero-engine fans.

However, due to the simple geometry of flat baffles, controlling the total pressure loss distribution within the generated distortion patterns is difficult, and consequently, the accuracy of the resulting patterns cannot be guaranteed.

In contrast, simulating plates offer the flexibility to adjust their shape, contour, and size according to the total pressure loss distribution of a target pattern. This capability allows for the generation of a wide range of distortion patterns with diverse shapes, enabling a more precise simulation of the target pattern.

By meticulously designing a bellmouth-shaped simulating plate, Bion et al. [15] experimentally and effectively simulated complex steady and unsteady inlet distortions, providing a reliable method to assess engine performance and surge margin under adverse inlet conditions during the early stages of development. Ye Wei et al. [16] proposed a semi-empirical design method for simulating plates that utilizes experimental data from flat baffles. The approximate contour of the simulating

plate is first determined based on the shape of the filled pattern, and then a modification plan is established according to the circumferential distortion intensity from wind tunnel test results. Lu Deyu et al. [17] experimentally investigated the design of scaled simulating plates and concluded that the various distortion indices of large-scale and small-scale models exhibit good correlation. Zhu Aidi [18] attempted to design the shape of a simulating plate based on a specific isoline within the total pressure recovery coefficient pattern. The results showed that it could replicate the general distribution of high and low-pressure regions, but the accuracy of the pattern and distortion indices needed improvement. Furthermore, it was difficult to establish a unified mapping relationship between the computational plane and the target distortion pattern.

On one hand, current design techniques for simulating plates are heavily reliant on empirical knowledge and distortion experiments. The design process requires repeated adjustments and experiments, leading to long development cycles and high costs to obtain a plate that can generate the target pattern. Considering the advantages of numerical simulation—namely its speed, low cost, and safety—it is feasible to design simulating plates using numerical methods to efficiently replicate the target patterns.

On the other hand, a common approach in existing design methods is to directly use the low total pressure region of the target pattern as the contour for the simulating plate. While this method can generate distortion in specific areas of the AIP, the shape and contour of the distorted region often differs significantly from those of the plate. The discrepancy arises because vortices are generated in the downstream flow field due to pressure gradients, and these vortices alter the shape of the distortion zone, causing the design to deviate from the intended target.

To address the issues of long design cycles and insufficient accuracy, this paper utilizes the shape of the simulating plate to control the magnitude and distribution of the pressure gradient, thereby altering the vorticity distribution. This vorticity distribution is then used to influence the configuration of the low-pressure zone. Ultimately, a high-precision distortion simulating plate is constructed in just two iterations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, a duct with an inner diameter (D) of 450 mm is used to represent the engine inlet. To mitigate the influence of inlet and outlet boundary conditions on the flow field, and to account for the size and location of the recirculation zone behind the plate, the simulating plate is positioned 2D downstream from the inlet plane. The Aerodynamic Interface Plane (AIP) is located 2D downstream of the plate, and the outlet plane is set at 10D downstream from the plate.

FIGURE 2: 3D VIEW OF THE SIMULATING PLATE

FIGURE 3: COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN AND DEFINITIONS OF KEY PLANES

Simulations are conducted in ANSYS CFX using the Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model. The working fluid is modeled as an ideal gas, and the inlet conditions are set to standard atmospheric conditions. Mesh refinement is applied near walls and around the simulating plate to meet Y^+ requirements.

A grid independence study was conducted on the computational mesh. Models with element counts ranging from 2.1 to 7.3 million were calculated to obtain the curve of the distortion coefficient, $DC(120)$, at the AIP versus the number of grid elements. The results indicate that when the element count exceeds 3 million, the aerodynamic parameters at the AIP show no significant changes. Therefore, the element count for all cases presented in this paper is maintained at approximately 3 million, thus meeting the grid independence requirement.

FIGURE 4: GRID INDEPENDENCE

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Influence of Simulating Plate Geometric Features on Distortion Development

Through the study of simulating plates with various shapes, it was found that their geometric features exert a similar influence on the flow field and the resulting distortion patterns. This paper uses a sectoral-annular simulating plate, as shown in FIGURE 5, as a case study to illustrate how variations in fundamental geometric features affect the flow field.

FIGURE 5: DEFINITION OF GEOMETRIC PARAMETERS

The relative width, L , and relative height, H , are defined as:

$$L = \frac{\theta}{2\pi} \quad (1)$$

$$H = \frac{h}{D} \quad (2)$$

where θ is the central angle of the sectoral-annular plate, h is the height of the plate as shown in the diagram, and D is the diameter of the inlet duct.

To quantify the magnitude of the distortion, this paper adopts the circumferential total pressure distortion index, $DC(120)$, developed by Rolls-Royce:

$$DC(120) = \frac{Pt_0 - Pt_{low}}{Pt_0 - P_0} \quad (3)$$

where Pt_0 is the mass-flow averaged total pressure at the inlet plane, Pt_{low} is the mass-flow averaged total pressure within the most distorted 120-degree sector at the AIP, and P_0 is the average static pressure at the inlet.

As shown in FIGURE 6, an almost linear relationship exists between the relative height (H) of the simulating plate and the area of the low-pressure region in the resulting distortion pattern. The increase in the plate's area due to a larger H is smaller than the corresponding increase in the low-pressure area at the AIP. This implies that a minor change in the plate's area leads to a more significant change in the low-pressure area of the distortion

pattern; for instance, a 10% increase in plate area results in an average increase of 31% in the low-pressure area at the AIP.

As can be seen in FIGURE 7, the higher the simulating plate, the greater its blockage effect on the airflow, which in turn leads to a larger distortion index. Furthermore, the extent to which the distortion coefficient is affected by H varies at different downstream locations. In this paper, the section from the simulating plate to the 1D plane is defined as the near-wake region, and the section downstream of 1D plane is defined as the far-wake region. In the near-wake region, as the H increases, the growth rate of the distortion index gradually slows down, indicating that a larger relative height H weakens the influence of H on the distortion index. In the far-wake region, however, the distortion coefficient exhibits a nearly linear variation with H . The distortion coefficient upstream of 1D is significantly higher than that in the 2D region, suggesting that the distortion mechanisms in the near-wake and far-wake flow fields are different. This will be further analyzed later in the context of vorticity distribution.

FIGURE 6: EFFECT OF H ON LOW-PRESSURE AREA

FIGURE 7: EFFECT OF H ON DC(120) IN NEAR-WAKE AND FAR-WAKE REGIONS

As can be seen in FIGURE 8, both the area of the simulating plate and the area of the low-pressure region increase linearly with the relative width, L . Furthermore, the extent of the increase in the low-pressure area is greater than that of the simulating plate's area. By analyzing the distortion index at different locations downstream of the distortion screen, as shown in FIGURE 9, it is observed that when the relative width L increases from 0.167 to 0.25, the growth rate of the distortion index varies with L , following a trend similar to that of the screen height effect.

FIGURE 8: EFFECT OF L ON LOW-PRESSURE AREA

FIGURE 9: EFFECT OF L ON DC(120) IN NEAR-WAKE AND FAR-WAKE REGIONS

FIGURE 10 shows that in the near-wake region, the area of the low-pressure region gradually increases with the development of the recirculation zone. In the far-wake region, however, primarily due to the mixing effect between fluids from the high and low-pressure regions, the size of the low-pressure area decreases in a nearly linear fashion.

FIGURE 10: STREAMWISE VARIATION OF THE LOW-PRESSURE AREA

3.2 Vorticity Distribution Characteristics and Generation Mechanism Downstream of the Simulating Plate

FIGURE 11 illustrates the distribution of vortex structures in the flow field, with the contours showing the total pressure on an iso-surface defined by the Q-criterion [19] at a value of 4000. From the figure, it is evident that the vortices are primarily distributed in the region immediately downstream of and adjacent to the simulating plate. In the plate's near-wake region, the upstream flow is obstructed by the plate, forming a horseshoe vortex that gradually weakens as it develops downstream. The corner vortices do not fully mix and dissipate with other vortices, which results in the formation of two small low-total-pressure zones at corresponding locations on the distortion pattern at the AIP.

FIGURE 11: VORTEX STRUCTURES AND TOTAL PRESSURE

As shown in FIGURE 12, the vorticity is strongest at the interface between the high and low-pressure regions downstream of the plate and gradually diminishes along the flow path due to streamwise development and fluid mixing. Consequently, the influence of vorticity on the flow field is more significant in the near-wake region. As the flow progresses downstream into the far-wake region, the vorticity level decreases, and its impact on the total pressure loss distribution weakens accordingly.

To further analyze the evolution mechanism of the low-pressure region, this study divides the flow into two stages based on vorticity magnitude: the first stage, the near-wake region from

the simulating plate to the 1D plane, where changes in the low-pressure region are predominantly governed by vorticity; and the second stage, the far-wake region from 1D to the 2D plane (as seen in FIGURE 13), where the vorticity has significantly weakened, and the dominant influencing factor on the low-pressure region shifts to the mixing between fluids from the high and low-pressure zones. This mixing action leads to a more uniform total pressure distribution at the interface of the high and low-pressure areas and simultaneously reduces the overall area of the low-pressure region.

FIGURE 12: STREAMWISE DISTRIBUTION OF VORTICITY

FIGURE 13: STREAMWISE EVOLUTION OF VORTICITY DISTRIBUTION AND THE LOW-PRESSURE REGION

Through analysis of the downstream flow field, this study finds that the magnitude and distribution of the pressure gradient behind the simulating plate determine the distribution of vorticity. According to the findings of Antoniou et al. [20], flow separation originates at the leading edge of the plate, forming a large recirculation zone downstream. Within this zone, the fluid flows from the distorted region toward the undistorted region (FIGURE 14).

FIGURE 14: PRESSURE GRADIENT AND FLOW VECTORS AT SIMULATING PLATE EDGE

A schematic of the vortex generation is shown in FIGURE 15. Under the influence of an adverse pressure gradient, the component of the fluid's velocity parallel to the gradient direction decreases, resulting in a deflection of the resultant velocity vector. As the angle between the fluid velocity vector and the adverse pressure gradient vector varies at different locations, the fluid undergoes varying degrees of deflection, manifesting as the formation of vortices in the cross-sectional plane. Therefore, the vorticity distribution can be controlled by manipulating the magnitude and distribution of the pressure gradient.

FIGURE 15: MECHANISM OF VORTEX GENERATION VIA VELOCITY VECTOR DEFLECTION BY AN ADVERSE PRESSURE GRADIENT

3.3 Influence of Vorticity on the Low-Pressure Region

The distribution and evolution of vortex structures significantly impact the shape and contour of the low-pressure region as the fluid develops downstream.

Since vortices are generated when the fluid flows against an adverse pressure gradient, their locations largely coincide with regions of high pressure gradient, namely, near the interface between the high and low-pressure zones. Consequently, as the flow progresses downstream, the stronger vortex structures continuously influence the shape of the low-pressure region at its boundary.

As seen in FIGURE 16, there are three pairs of counter-rotating vortices at the edge of the low-pressure region at the 0.5D downstream location. Taking the central vortex pair as an example, with the flow direction pointing into the page, blue indicates counter-clockwise rotation and red indicates clockwise rotation. Under the influence of this vortex pair, the boundary of the distortion zone expands outward in the region between them. Therefore, under the influence of these three vortex pairs, the contour of the distortion zone at the 1D location evolves into a shape that bulges outward in three primary directions, with the resulting low-pressure distribution shown in the figure.

FIGURE 16: VORTEX INFLUENCE ON DISTORTION SHAPE

Therefore, to generate the low-pressure region of a target distortion pattern, the shape and contour of the simulating plate are first controlled to regulate the vorticity distribution. The influence of this vorticity on the flow structure is then leveraged to adjust the extent of the distortion region, ultimately achieving precise control over its shape and contour.

FIGURE 17: FLOWCHART OF THE PHYSICAL MECHANISM CONTROLLING THE DISTORTION REGION SHAPE

3.4 Design Method for Simulating Plates Based on Vorticity Distribution

In conventional design methods for simulating plates, the plate's contour is typically derived directly from the low total pressure region of the target pattern. While this approach can generate distortion within a specific area at the AIP, the distribution and magnitude of the loss in the distorted region often differ significantly from the target, making it difficult to achieve the required design accuracy. Enhancing the design accuracy of total pressure distortion patterns involves two primary aspects: the shape and contour of the low-pressure region, and the magnitude of the pressure loss within it. Based on the previously discussed flow characteristics, including the evolution of vorticity and pressure gradients downstream of the distortion screen, this study adopts FIGURE 18 as the target distortion pattern and investigates improvement methods for enhancing the accuracy of the designed distortion pattern with respect to the two aforementioned aspects.

FIGURE 18: TARGET PATTERN

3.4.1 Generation of the Low-Pressure Region Contour

First, the "No. 1 Simulating Plate" is constructed using the contour of the low-pressure region from the target pattern as its shape, resulting in the plate shown in FIGURE 19. Applying the principles of vorticity generation discussed in the previous section, it can be predicted that two pairs of counter-rotating vortices will form in regions 1 and 2, respectively. These vortex pairs will cause the low-pressure region to expand outward in directions 3 and 4. Through numerical simulation, the distortion pattern generated by this plate at the AIP is obtained, as shown in FIGURE 20. This demonstrates that, with the traditional design method of directly using the target pattern's low-pressure shape as the simulating plate's contour, the resulting distortion pattern differs significantly from the target in terms of both the shape and the location of the loss distribution in the low-pressure region.

FIGURE 19: NO. 1 SIMULATING PLATE

FIGURE 20: REFERENCE PATTERN

The contour of the low-pressure region from FIGURE 20 is then extracted to serve as the outer contour for a new "No. 2 Simulating Plate," as depicted in FIGURE 21. Again applying the principles of vorticity generation, it is predicted that the "No. 2 Simulating Plate" will create a vortex pair in region 1. This vortex pair will cause the low-pressure area to expand outward in direction 2, thereby aligning the distribution of the low-pressure region more closely with that of the target pattern. A numerical simulation of the "No. 2 Simulating Plate" yields the total pressure distortion pattern at the AIP, as shown in FIGURE 22. A comparison of this pattern's shape with that of the target distortion pattern reveals that by leveraging the influence of vorticity distribution in two iterative steps, the shape and distribution of the low-pressure region in the designed pattern achieve close agreement with the target (FIGURE 23).

FIGURE 21: NO. 2 SIMULATING PLATE

FIGURE 22: RESULTING DESIGNED PATTERN

The key characteristic of the "No. 2 Simulating Plate" is that the distortion pattern it generates is similar in shape to the target pattern's low-pressure region. However, at this stage, the relative errors between the generated pattern and the target pattern in terms of distortion coefficient and low-pressure area are approximately 12.3% and 11.6%, respectively. Therefore, further control over the magnitude of the pressure loss is still required.

FIGURE 23: COMPARISON OF THE CONTOUR BETWEEN THE DESIGNED AND TARGET PATTERNS

3.4.2 Control of the Loss Magnitude in the Low-Pressure Region

After obtaining the shape of the "No. 2 Simulating Plate", the next step is to adjust the area and the magnitude of loss in the low-pressure region.

First, the location of the AIP in the far-wake region is determined, and the boundary of the low-pressure region at this location is defined as the design target of this stage. By non-dimensionalizing the "reference pattern" shown in FIGURE 20, the distribution of the relative total pressure coefficient across the surface can be obtained. From this reference pattern, it is observed that its boundary lies within the geometric range corresponding to a relative total pressure coefficient of 0.1 to 0.2. This allows for the plotting of a series of relative total pressure coefficient isolines, as shown in FIGURE 24. These curves are geometrically similar but enclose different areas. By selecting different isolines as the outer contours to construct a series of simulating plates, the degree of flow blockage produced by these plates varies monotonically with their area. Due to their geometric similarity, the vortex structures generated by these plates are also similar under the same inflow Mach number. Consequently, the shapes of the resulting low-pressure regions are all similar to that of the target distortion pattern. Thus, by iteratively selecting isolines of different values, it is possible to control the degree of flow blockage from the simulating plate. This allows for the adjustment of the distortion coefficient, low-pressure area, and the average total pressure within the low-pressure region of the designed pattern, bringing them into closer alignment with the target.

FIGURE 24: RELATIVE TOTAL PRESSURE COEFFICIENT ISOLINES

FIGURE 25: FLOWCHART OF THE SIMULATING PLATE DESIGN METHOD

During the isoline selection process, given that the loss magnitude increases monotonically with the simulating plate's area, a bisection method can be used to select the isoline. Typically, a suitable isoline can be identified within two iterations. This paper presents the design results for distortion patterns generated using the relative total pressure coefficient of 0.10, 0.12, and 0.14. The resulting loss magnitudes at the AIP are detailed in Table 1. The table indicates that as the simulating plate area increases, the distortion coefficient and the low-pressure area of the generated pattern also increase, while the average total pressure of the cross-section and the average total pressure within the low-pressure region both decrease. Based on

these results, the simulating plate constructed from the isoline with a value of 0.12 yields a loss magnitude that most closely matches the target pattern in this case.

FIGURE 26: COMPARISON OF TARGET AND DESIGNED DISTORTION PATTERNS

TABLE 1: QUANTITATIVE COMPARISON OF DISTORTION PARAMETERS BETWEEN THE TARGET AND DESIGNED PATTERNS

	Plate Area (m ²)	DC(120)	Low-Pressure Area (m ²)	Plane Avg. Total Pressure (Pa)	Low-Pressure Avg. Total Pressure (Pa)
Target Pattern	-	68.2474%	0.0370212	101276	101057
0.10 Plate	0.027287	59.8673%	0.032734	101281	101080
0.12 Plate	0.029501	68.1111%	0.0373617	101277	101058
0.14 Plate	0.031437	73.8314%	0.040841	101265	101036

4. CONCLUSION

Through the investigation of the design technology for simulating plate-type total pressure distortion generators, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. By studying the influence of the simulating plate's typical geometric features on the distortion coefficient and pattern, it was found that an increase in H and L leads to a nearly linear increase in the distortion coefficient at the AIP in the far-wake region. In the near-wake region, however, the rate of increase of the distortion coefficient decelerates as H and L increase. Moreover, the distortion index in the near-wake region is significantly higher than that in the far-wake region.
2. Downstream of the simulating plate, an angle between the fluid velocity vector and the adverse pressure gradient vector leads to the formation of multiple vortex structures between the high and low-pressure fluids. These vortex structures alter the contour of the distortion region's boundary according to the vortex orientation, thereby enabling control over the distortion contour through the manipulation of the vorticity distribution.
3. By leveraging the principles of vorticity influence, an inverse design method for the simulating plate was developed based on the distribution of the low-pressure region. To address the inaccuracy of patterns generated by conventional methods, this approach first obtains a plate capable of producing the desired vortex

structures through a two-step iteration, bringing the designed low-pressure contour close to the target. Second, it iteratively selects a suitable relative total pressure coefficient to construct a geometrically similar plate, ensuring the loss magnitude in the designed pattern closely matches that of the target.

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